

The Triple Burden of Belief: Socio-Religious and Traditional Barriers to the Clinical Management of Malaria, Typhoid, and Hepatitis in Pankshin LGA of Nigeria

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Abstract

Malaria, typhoid fever, and viral hepatitis constitute a persistent triple infectious burden in rural Nigeria, where socio-religious norms and traditional beliefs intersect with limited healthcare access to influence disease outcomes. This study examined the socio-religious and traditional barriers affecting the clinical management of these infections in eight communities of Pankshin Local Government Area (LGA), Plateau State, north-central Nigeria. A community-based cross-sectional survey was conducted among 80 adult residents, selected purposively to represent diverse socio-demographic and cultural backgrounds. Data were collected using structured, interviewer-administered questionnaires and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics in R software, with spatial mapping in ArcGIS to visualise patterns of awareness and treatment-seeking behaviour. Results indicate that while general awareness of malaria, typhoid, and hepatitis was moderate to high, in-depth knowledge regarding transmission, prevention, and clinical care was limited. A significant proportion of respondents relied on traditional medicine (47.7%)

or spiritual healing, influenced by beliefs in supernatural causation, perceived efficacy of indigenous remedies, and religious doctrines. Hospital care was the first point of contact for 73.3% of participants; however, 25.6% sought chemists, herbalists, or prayer houses first, creating delays in diagnosis and treatment. Physical discomfort, access challenges, and cost further reinforced these barriers. Associations between educational level and health-seeking behaviour were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The study highlights the "Triple Burden of Belief," where socio-religious, cultural, and structural factors jointly impede effective clinical management. To mitigate these barriers, culturally sensitive health education, engagement of traditional and religious leaders as referral partners, and improved access to affordable diagnostics and treatment are recommended. Addressing these intersecting challenges is critical to reducing morbidity and mortality from malaria, typhoid, and hepatitis in rural Nigerian communities.

Keywords: *Malaria, Typhoid, Hepatitis, Socio-Religious, Beliefs, Traditional, Barriers.*

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Introduction

Malaria, typhoid fever, and viral hepatitis together represent a persistent triple infectious burden in Nigeria, especially in rural communities where poverty, weak health systems, and limited diagnostics converge to sustain high morbidity and mortality. Both diseases, mainly associated with poverty and underdevelopment with significant morbidity and mortality, are common in many countries where the prevailing environmental conditions of warm humid climate, poor sanitary habits, poverty, and ignorance exist (Saleh et al., 2020)

Malaria remains hyper-endemic and is a leading cause of fever, particularly among children and pregnant women, with frequent overlap in clinical presentation with typhoid fever, which complicates accurate diagnosis and timely treatment (Lawal et al., 2025; Olowolafe et al., 2024). Malaria is a life-threatening disease caused by protozoan parasites belonging to genus *Plasmodium* that are transmitted through the bites of infected female *Anopheles* mosquitoes. This disease causes widespread deaths to children and economic hardships on poor household families. Malaria causes symptoms that typically include fever, fatigue, vomiting, and headaches. In severe cases, it can cause yellow skin, seizures,

coma, or death (Mohammed et al., 2020). In the year 2018, WHO estimates that there were about 228 million cases of malaria and 405,000 malaria-related deaths with 93.8% of deaths occurring in sub-Saharan Africa (Chipoya & Shima-ponda-Mataa, 2020). The majority of infections are caused by *Plasmodium falciparum* species, the most dangerous of the four human malaria parasites (Nodem et al., 2023).

Typhoid fever is an acute systemic infection caused by *Salmonella typhi*, a Gram and oxidase-negative bacterium. It is mainly transmitted faeco-orally through contaminated food and water. There are about 33 million cases of typhoid annually in the world resulting in 216,000 deaths in endemic areas. Outbreaks of typhoid fever are frequently reported from sub-Saharan Africa and countries in Southeast Asia. WHO identifies typhoid as a serious public health problem with high incidence on children, young adults, and pregnant women. The most prominent feature of the infection is fever, which gradually rises to a high value. High fever, lethargy, skin rash, loss of appetite, constipation more than often, abdominal pain, diarrhea, hepatosplenomegaly, bradycardia, and headaches are the commonest symptoms, and without treatment, symptoms may last for weeks

or months (World Health Organization (WHO), 2014; Ubengama, et al., 2019; Ia & Mo, 2020).

Viral hepatitis is one of the communicable diseases for which deaths are increasing. About 1.3 million people died of viral hepatitis in 2022, similar to the number of deaths caused by tuberculosis. Viral hepatitis and tuberculosis were the second leading causes of death among communicable diseases in 2022, after COVID-19 (WHO, 2024). Viral hepatitis affects more than 300 million people globally. Most people are not diagnosed or getting the treatment they need. Each day, 3,500 people die from liver disease caused by viral hepatitis worldwide. Safe and effective vaccines, prevention, and treatments can avert liver disease and cancer caused by viral hepatitis. Increasing intervention and prevention methods can save money and lives (Center for Disease Control (CDC), 2025),

Co-infection of malaria and typhoid is common in both rural and urban Nigerian settings, with reported co-infection prevalence frequently exceeding 30%, and highest rates often observed among young adults, women, and children (Magaji & Mahnud, 2025; Miller Melford et al., 2025; Adamu et al., 2023). Viral hepatitis B and C further add a largely silent but significant contribution to liver-related morbidity, with non-trivial prevalence documented in Nigerian hospital populations (Ademoyegun & Aremu, 2024; Uzoka et al., 2021).

Biomedical analyses often emphasize climatic, environmental, and socioeconomic determinants of these infections (Dawaki et al., 2016; Uzoka et al., 2021). However, in rural Nigeria, the persistence and clinical management of malaria, typhoid, and hepatitis cannot be fully understood without examining belief systems, socio-religious norms, and traditional healing practices. Qualitative and mixed-methods studies from Nigeria and similar West African contexts show that, although many community members express a preference for hospital care, they frequently default to traditional healers and patent medicine vendors due to high user fees, distance to facilities, language barriers, and the need to balance illness with subsistence work (Bedford & Sharkey, 2014; Tiv & Friant, 2021). In many settings, diseases are simultaneously

understood through biomedical and spiritual frames; some illnesses are attributed to witchcraft, sin, or “bad behaviour,” with stigma and fear shaping when and where patients seek help (Tiv & Friant, 2021).

Religious and cultural structures specifically influence women’s and caregivers’ health-seeking behaviour in Nigeria. Ethnographic work on maternal health documents how dependence on prayer houses, the authority of religious leaders, lack of women’s autonomy, and the use of herbal medicine can delay or substitute for formal facility-based care (Opara et al., 2024). Studies of childhood illness and integrated community case management similarly show that misconceptions about the severity of malaria and other infections, combined with strong religious barriers, limit timely use of available biomedical services (Amzat & Shehu, 2020; Bedford & Sharkey, 2014). At the same time, traditional medicine remains highly trusted, widely used, and historically important in the management of febrile illnesses such as malaria and typhoid, particularly in underserved rural areas (Gabriel, 2023; Onukansi et al., 2025).

Within this socio-cultural landscape, the clinical management of malaria, typhoid, and hepatitis in rural Nigeria is constrained not only by diagnostic limitations and health-system weaknesses but also by a triple burden of belief: (1) religious doctrines and practices that may discourage or delay biomedical care; (2) culturally embedded trust in traditional and herbal remedies, often used as alternatives to formal treatment; and (3) persistent misconceptions about disease causation, severity, and curability. These belief-mediated barriers can exacerbate diagnostic confusion, particularly for malaria–typhoid co-infection, contribute to delayed presentation, inappropriate self-medication and antibiotic misuse, and foster poor adherence to treatment, thereby increasing the risks of complications, antimicrobial resistance, and preventable deaths (Adamu et al., 2023; Akinyemi et al., 2018; Lawal et al., 2025; Musa et al., 2025).

Hence, this study was to examine how socio-religious beliefs and traditional practices

Data Collection Instrument

Primary data were obtained using a structured questionnaire designed specifically for this research. The questionnaire comprised sections addressing respondents' socio-demographic profiles, awareness and understanding of malaria, typhoid fever, and viral hepatitis, perceived causes and seriousness of the disease, patterns of treatment-seeking behaviour, and barriers to accessing formal healthcare services. The instrument was reviewed by specialists in public health, epidemiology, and social research to enhance clarity, relevance, and cultural appropriateness for rural settings.

Validity and Reliability

To assess reliability, the questionnaire was pre-tested using a test-retest approach in a rural community outside the study area. The instrument was administered twice to 10 respondents at a two-week interval, and the responses were analysed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. The resulting correlation value ($r \geq 0.85$) indicated a high level of reliability and temporal stability.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected through interviewer-administered questionnaires conducted by trained field assistants who were conversant with the local language and cultural context. This method enhanced comprehension and accuracy of responses, particularly among participants with limited formal education. Geographic coordinates of respondents' households were recorded using handheld Garmin eTrex 10 GPS devices to support spatial analysis of the study locations.

Data Management and Analysis

Completed questionnaires were reviewed for accuracy and completeness before data entry into Microsoft Excel and subsequent analysis using R statistical software (version 4.5.2). Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarise key variables. Inferential analyses, such as chi-square tests and Fisher's exact tests, were applied to explore associations between socio-demographic factors and

awareness or treatment-seeking behaviour, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Spatial data were processed and visualised using ArcGIS Pro (version 3.6). GIS tools were employed to map the spatial distribution of study communities and observed patterns of awareness and treatment-seeking behaviour, thereby providing geographical context to the study findings.

Figure 2. Responses of Residents from Eight Rural Communities in Pankshin Local Government Area, Plateau State, Nigeria, Regarding Local Beliefs Discouraging the Use of Insecticide-Treated Nets

Figure 3. Primary Factors Influencing Avoidance of Insecticide-Treated Nets among Study Participants in Rural Communities of Pankshin LGA Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 4. Use of Mosquito Nets by Respondents According to Religious Affiliation in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 5. Perceived Factors Influencing the Choice of Non-Hospital Care (Traditional Medicine and Prayer/Spiritual Healing) for the Treatment of Hepatitis in Rural Communities of Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 6. Reported Socio-Religious and Traditional Barriers to the Clinical Management of Hepatitis, Malaria, and Typhoid in Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 7. First Point of Care Sought during Illness among Residents of Rural Communities in Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Results

The empirical data gathered from the eight communities of Pankshin LGA illuminates the intricate relationship between belief systems and clinical outcomes. The survey identifies that while modern medical awareness is present, a "Triple Burden" of socio-religious and traditional frameworks continues to mediate healthcare utilization.

The Burden of Misconception and Behavioral Barriers

Local beliefs significantly interfere with established preventive measures for vector-borne diseases. Regarding the utilization of Insecticide-Treated Nets (ITNs), spatial variation is prominent (Fig. 2). While communities like Dimwai (80%) and Kor (72.7%) largely report that local beliefs do not discourage use, a substantial minority in Fumbis (45.5%) and Nungwus (27.3%) explicitly acknowledge that traditional beliefs act as a direct deterrent to this clinical intervention.

The primary barrier to ITN utilization, however, is a combination of physiological and ideological factors. As illustrated in Fig. 3, 69.1% of respondents avoid insecticide-treated bed net use due to "Heat/Discomfort," while cultural/belief barriers (11.1%) and lack of access (11.1%) constitute the remaining obstacles. This environment allows for the

continued circulation of pathogens, even when the technology for prevention is available.

Belief-Mediated Barriers to Malaria Prevention

Religious affiliation serves as a secondary layer of the dictating the frequency of preventive adherence (Fig. 4). While Christian and Muslim respondents show higher rates of nightly ITN use, those identifying with African Traditional Religion, ATR report the highest rates of "Rarely/Never" use (approximately 33.3%).

Initial Health-Seeking Pathways

Analysis of initial health-seeking behavior (Fig. 7) shows that 73.3% (n=63) of respondents visit the hospital as their first point of care. However, an "informal leakage" of 25.6% occurs, where individuals prioritize Chemists (15.1%), Herbalists (7.0%), or Prayer houses (3.5%). This minority group operates largely outside the clinical framework, often presenting at facilities only after complications such as the intestinal perforations noted by 75.6% of respondents have developed.

Discussion

The Ecology of Faith and Clinical Conflict

The findings of this study confirm that the clinical management of Malaria, Typhoid, and Hepatitis in rural Nigeria is not merely a logistical challenge but a profound conflict between "sacred beliefs and secular science." This "Triple Burden of Belief" creates a non-clinical gap that persists despite the theoretical availability of modern medicine.

Initial Health-Seeking Behavior and Informal Leakage

Although hospitals were identified as the first point of care by 73.3% of respondents, a critical 25.6% initially sought care from chemists (15.1%), herbalists (7.0%), or prayer houses (3.5%). This "informal leakage" represents a major non-clinical gap within the healthcare system. Chemist visits often involve unsupervised self-medication, while prayer houses and herbalists delay biomedical diagnosis. By the time patients transition to hospitals, complications such as intestinal

perforations reported by 75.6% of respondents are more likely to have developed.

This pattern reflects the first delay in the "Three Delays Model," where the decision to seek care is shaped by spiritual interpretation rather than clinical urgency (Nas et al., 2017). Consistent with Bedford and Sharkey (2014) and Opara et al. (2024), religious and traditional leaders function as powerful gatekeepers whose influence can either obstruct or facilitate timely clinical care.

Socio-Religious View and Clinical Delay

The disparity in ITN use among traditionalists (Fig. 4) and the reliance on prayer houses (Fig. 7) underscore the role of religious leaders as the primary gatekeepers of health behavior. As noted by Opara et al. (2024), the authority of religious leaders and the dependence on prayer houses often substitute for formal care. In Pankshin, this results in a "dangerous clinical delay." When 10.5% of the population utilizes prayer houses or herbalists as a first contact point, the biological window for treating acute malaria or preventing typhoid complications closes. This aligns with the "Three Delays" model, where the first delay the decision to seek care is mediated by a spiritual lens that perceives illness as a supernatural occurrence rather than a biological one (Nas et al., 2017; Tiv & Friant, 2021).

Religious affiliation further stratifies preventive adherence. Christian and Muslim respondents reported higher rates of nightly ITN use, whereas individuals practicing traditional religions showed the highest proportion of "rarely" or "never" using nets ($\approx 33\%$). This disparity underscores the role of religious worldviews in shaping acceptance of biomedical interventions. In such contexts, illness is often framed within spiritual causation, reducing the perceived necessity of clinical prevention (Tiv & Friant, 2021).

This socio-religious filtering becomes more pronounced in the management of chronic infections, particularly viral hepatitis. Nearly half of respondents (47.7%) who avoided hospital care did so because they believed traditional or spiritual treatments were more effective than

biomedical options. This perception far outweighed economic explanations such as cost (24.4%) or adherence to cultural tradition (10.5%). The dominance of perceived efficacy reflects deep trust in indigenous healing systems, especially for illnesses viewed as slow, hidden, or morally stigmatized, such as hepatitis (Uzoka et al., 2021; Tiv & Friant, 2021).

The Traditional Trust and Medical Pluralism

The fact that 47.7% of respondents perceive traditional medicine as "more effective" than hospital care (Fig. 5) suggests that biomedical interventions are often viewed as insufficient for "spiritual" diseases. This is particularly evident in Hepatitis management, where symptoms are frequently attributed to "promiscuity" or social transgressions, creating a stigma-based barrier to clinical management (Tiv & Friant, 2021). Composite analysis across malaria, typhoid, and hepatitis reveals a consistent pattern of medical pluralism. While 31.4% of respondents believe traditional and hospital medicine should work together, this coexistence often produces clinical delay rather than complimentary. For typhoid, 12.8% attributed chronic infection to witchcraft, and 10.5% reported prayer houses or herbalists as their first point of care. Such supernatural causal beliefs undermine adherence to antibiotic regimens, as relapse is interpreted spiritually rather than biologically.

In malaria, resistance to ITN use whether framed as discomfort, cultural symbolism, or spiritual protection prevents the level of coverage required to interrupt transmission. For hepatitis, stigma linked to perceived promiscuity or moral transgression discourages early testing and sustained clinical engagement. These patterns align with previous findings that belief-mediated delays exacerbate disease severity, antimicrobial misuse, and preventable complications (Adamu et al., 2023; Akinoyemi et al., 2018). This state of "Medical Pluralism" where 31.4% believe traditional and hospital medicine should coexist reflects a community trying to bridge two worlds. However, as Gabriel (2023) and Onukansi et al. (2025) suggest, this trust in traditional remedies often leads to inappropriate self-medication and antibiotic

misuse, further complicating the clinical picture of malaria-typhoid co-infection (Adamu et al., 2023).

Utilization of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) illustrates how cultural and environmental factors intersect to undermine malaria prevention. Spatial variation across communities shows that while respondents in Dimwai (80%) and Kor (72.7%) largely reported that beliefs did not discourage ITN use, a substantial proportion in Fumbis (45.5%) and Nungwus (27.3%) identified traditional beliefs as direct deterrents. These findings indicate that malaria prevention is not uniformly interpreted as a biomedical necessity but is instead subject to localized cultural meaning.

However, the most dominant barrier to ITN use was not belief alone but physical discomfort. Nearly 70% of respondents cited heat and discomfort as the primary reason for non-use, with belief-related objections and lack of access each accounting for 11.1%. This finding reflects a critical perception gap: while communities recognize malaria as a threat, preventive tools are weighed against immediate bodily discomfort and cultural acceptability. Similar patterns have been reported in rural Nigerian and West African settings, where environmental discomfort and symbolic interpretations of nets limit consistent use (Amzat & Shehu, 2020; Dawaki et al., 2016).

In the context of chronic infections like Hepatitis, the preference for alternative care is driven by perceived efficacy rather than mere economic necessity. Fig. 5 reveals that 47.7% of respondents choose non-hospital care because they perceive it as "More effective," far outweighing those who choose it due to cost (24.4%) or cultural tradition (10.5%). This trust in indigenous "cures" over biomedical interventions is further reflected in the categorical challenges identified in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, where "Poor awareness" (33.3%) and "Cultural beliefs" are quantified as core obstacles alongside systemic issues like "No vaccine" and "Poor health facilities."

Environmental Persistence and the Perception Gap

The Results section highlights a significant perception gap: while environmental awareness of typhoid is high, 12.8% still attribute chronic infection to witchcraft. This "supernatural causal belief" acts as a barrier to completing antibiotic cycles. If a patient interprets a medical "relapse" as a spiritual attack, they are less likely to adhere to clinical follow-up. This environmental persistence is worsened by the "Heat/Discomfort" barrier to ITN use (Fig. 3). Despite the high prevalence of malaria (WHO, 2020), the physical discomfort of the net is weighed against the perceived spiritual or cultural risk, often resulting in non-use.

Implications for Public Health

The wide implication of this research is that public health strategies in rural Nigeria must move beyond infrastructure-only solutions. The "Triple Burden" identified here socio-religious, traditional, and structural means that providing vaccines or nets is insufficient if the "Filter of Belief" rejects them. To improve clinical outcomes for Malaria, Typhoid, and Hepatitis, interventions must engage the very structures that currently act as barriers. Religious and traditional leaders must be integrated as "referral partners" to ensure that the 25.6% of "informal leakage" is captured and redirected to clinical facilities before the onset of life-threatening complications (Bedford & Sharkey, 2014; Opara et al., 2024). That is to say, the persistence of these endemic diseases in Pankshin LGA is a social ecological issue. The conflict between the perceived effectiveness of traditional herbs and the clinical necessity of pharmaceuticals remains the primary obstacle to achieving the 100% coverage required to break transmission cycles and reduce the disproportionate burden of disease in rural Nigeria (Simon-Oke & Akinbote, 2020).

Conclusion

The clinical management of Malaria, Typhoid, and Hepatitis in rural Nigeria is inextricably linked to a "Triple Burden of Belief" that transcends simple infrastructure deficits. This study has demonstrated that even when clinical

trust is relatively high, socio-religious doctrines and a deep-seated reliance on traditional medicine act as significant filters, determining the speed and nature of healthcare seeking. The persistence of these diseases in Pankshin LGA is not merely a failure of biology but a reflection of a pluralistic medical landscape where spiritual interpretations of illness often override biomedical logic. While the majority of respondents identify the hospital as their primary choice, the "informal leakage" of over 25% to chemists and prayer houses creates a dangerous gap in early diagnosis. This delay is particularly catastrophic for malaria-typhoid co-infections and chronic hepatitis, where symptoms are often misattributed to supernatural causes or social transgressions. Ultimately, as long as traditional herbs are perceived as more "effective" than clinical pharmaceuticals for certain etiologies, the biological transmission cycles of these endemic diseases will remain unbroken.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are proposed to bridge the gap between belief and clinical management:

- **Integration of Traditional and Religious Leaders as Referral Partners:** Public health agencies should move beyond viewing traditional and religious leaders as obstacles and instead engage them as "First-Contact Referral Partners." By training these leaders to recognize early clinical danger signs of Malaria and Typhoid, the health system can ensure that patients currently utilizing spiritual healing loops are redirected to clinical facilities within the critical biological window.
- **Culturally Responsive Health Education (Deep Clinical Literacy):** Health campaigns must shift from basic awareness to "Deep Clinical Literacy." Instead of simply promoting preventive tools, education should specifically address the "Triple Burden" of misconceptions such as the belief that physical discomfort makes nets unusable or that chronic typhoid is a spiritual attack. Messaging should use local idioms to explain the biological mechanisms of disease.

- Decentralized and Subsidized Diagnostics: To combat the tendency toward informal self-medication, the government should subsidize Rapid Diagnostic Tests (RDTs) for Malaria and Hepatitis at the community level. By making clinical diagnosis as accessible as over-the-counter options, the financial barriers that currently drive patients toward informal sectors can be significantly reduced.
- Strengthening Medical Pluralism Frameworks: A formal collaborative framework should be established where traditional practitioners are registered and encouraged to refer "unresponsive" cases to hospitals without fear of social or professional repercussions. This would transform the current conflict between the "sacred and secular" into a coordinated pathway that prioritizes patient survival.
- Environmental and Structural Adaptation: To address the physiological barriers to preventive tool utilization, future distribution programs should prioritize the provision of materials with improved ventilation or support the integration of mosquito-proofing in rural housing designs. This addresses the discomfort of modern interventions while respecting the local environment.

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